

Entry #: 7

Date Submitted: 6/30/2021 7:23 PM

I. Overview

A. Registration

1. Today's Date

6/30/2021

2. Title

Periodistas en Red: Descubre los nuevos cursos y talleres con los que puedes obtener las herramientas necesarias para conectar con las audiencias digitales

3. Participants

Homero Hinojosa, América Aidé Zamudio, Alma Cecilia Barajas

4. Email

homerohinojosa@tec.mx

5. Sponsors

No

6. Running Comments - Project Registration

B. Goals

1. Rationale

Ofrecer un repositorio de opciones de formación profesional y de reaprendizaje a periodistas mexicanos para que desarrollen más competitividad profesional y conecten mejor con sus audiencias para cumplir su misión de informar y educar a la comunidad.

2. Focus

Cursos, talleres, diplomados, seminarios y webinars en Periodismo

3. Components

Un portal con opciones de formación en Periodismo

Una área de talleres y cursos que permite localizar la temática de aprendizaje de interés y segmentar por nivel de experiencia

Un calendario para ayudar en la programación de actividades por semana, mes o el año completo

Una área de blogs con consejos de expertos para orientar la formación deseada

Una área de herramientas y apps de utilidad para apoyar el aprendizaje

4. Data Units

Links a programas reconocidos de Periodismo, como la SIP, Knight Center y Sembramedia

Un plug-in de calendario para organizar sus opciones de formación

Contenidos de expertos y consultores en periodismo para la parte de blogs

Bibliografía de publicaciones recientes en Periodismo tradicional, Digital y Marketing que apoyen la formación

Links a apps y herramientas de valor periodístico

5. Running Comments - Project Goals

C. Users

1. Proposed Audience

Periodistas mexicanos profesionales que trabajan en medios: reporteros, editores y coordinadores Freelancers Creadores de Contenidos para Twitch, YouTube, Instagram, etc.

1a. Multi-audience Goals

Profesionales que trabajan en medios: reporteros, editores y coordinadores
Freelancers
Creadores de Contenidos para Twitch, YouTube, Instagram, etc.

2. Use

Los visitantes al portal Periodistas En Red podrán navegar por las diferentes opciones de formación y escoger entre el repertorio una serie de cursos y talleres, calendalizarlos y aplicar a ellos. También podrán complementar esta experiencia de usuario con consejos y orientación que obtendrán a través de la lectura de blogs y consejos de expertos sobre oportunidades de formación que demanda el mercado laboral y de construcción de marca personal emprendedora.

3. Running Comments - Users**II. Components and Resources****A. Digital Objects**

1. Raw Materials: Specify the raw materials you will use to create the digital objects used in your project:

a. Texts

Yes

i. Text type: previously published?

Yes

ii. Text type: archival

No

iii. Text type: newly created

Yes

b. Images

Yes

i. Image type: photos

Yes

ii. Image type: digital scans

No

iii. Image type: line illustrations

No

iv. Image type: three-dimensional scans/renderings

No

c. Maps

No

d. Other

No

2. Tools and Formats: Specify the digital tools, file formats, or applications you will use for each of the raw materials chosen above (fields will appear according to the choices made above).

a.i. previously published texts - digital file formats

Microsoft Word

a.iii. newly created texts - digital file formats

Microsoft Word

b.i. photos - digital file formats

.jpg .png

3. User Interface (UI): If possible, identify a possible UI or web platform for your project. The proposed UI/platform must support the applications, tools, file formats, etc. listed above.

a. Chosen UI/platform with version and date of release.

Para el desarrollo de este proyecto utilizaremos dos plataformas que funcionarán en conjunto y que se complementarán una a la otra debido a las diferentes capacidades de cada una.

Google Sites: Será utilizado para el desarrollo de la plataforma y servirá de soporte para alojar las diferentes funcionalidades, entre ellos, información del proyecto, calendario, blogs, respaldo de la información.

Shiny App: A través de esta plataforma crearemos la interfaz que alojará la sección donde los usuarios podrán visualizar y elegir la información relacionada con los cursos. El desarrollo de la aplicación se realizará a través de la RStudio en su modalidad de escritorio pero la visualización web estará respaldada por la versión online de Shiny Cloud.

4. File Maintenance Tools: Indicate how the data making up these objects will be organized, stored, and accessed during the development and active phases.

a. Indicate where your digital objects will be uploaded, stored and accessed:

Google Drive

b. Choose a location platform for project files.

Google Drive

5. Running Comments - Digital Objects

6. Passwords: Lost passwords for databases, UI platforms, and other resources can stop a promising project in its tracks. It is important, therefore, to keep a durable record of all passwords, and make sure that project collaborators have access to them.

a. Would you like to archive your project's passwords here?

No

B. Resources

1. Skills and Personnel: List the skills needed and possible personnel for each of the digital objects specified above.

For example, will there be a team member(s) responsible for writing historical summaries? Scanning objects? Processing that scan data to create 3D renderings? Producing maps? Identifying the information to be included on those maps? Compiling bibliographies of pertinent sources?

a.i. previously published texts - skills and/or personnel

Un editor general que editará y curará material

a.iii. newly created texts - skills and/or personnel

Un editor general responsable del sitio

Un editor técnico que actualice y cuide la vigencia de los cursos y talleres

Dos bloggers que ofrezcan consejos publicando cada semana

b.i. photos - skills and/or personnel

El editor técnico con manejo de photoshop y edición fotográfica

b.ii. digital scans - skills and/or personnel**b. iv. three-dimensional scans/renderings - skills and personnel**

2. File Maintenance Personnel: Indicate who will organize, store, and make program files accessible during the development and active phases of the project.

a. Name of person charged with file maintenance

Aidé América Zamudio

b. Email of person charged with file maintenance

A00963836@itesm.mx

3. Start-up and long term costs: List the resources required to initiate, continue, and complete this project, including personnel, technology, associated fees and permissions costs.

a. Will you have associated personnel?

No

b. Will you have technology costs?

Yes

b. i. Technical: computer costs

pending

b. ii. Technical: laboratory costs

pending

b. iii. Technical: archival costs

pending

b. iv. Technical: other associated costs

pending

c. Will you have royalties or access /use fees

No

4. Permissions: Plan now to obtain written permission for the intellectual property the project will feature.**a. Have you drafted contributors' agreements for content creators?**

No

b. If you are working with materials from museums, libraries, or other institutional actors, will they require memoranda of understanding?

Yes

Have you drafted an MOU?

No

c. If your project has an institutional sponsor (university, museum, foundation, etc.), are there any administrative permissions or clearances required by that sponsor?

Yes

If you have received written permissions, upload a pdf of them here.

5. Running Comments - Resources

III. Trajectory

In order to implement your project, you will need to assemble the constituent parts identified above, and put them into a coherent relationship with one another. This will require you to identify the discrete tasks you will need to undertake in order to complete this project, and then establish the project's proposed trajectory and timeline.

To create such a timeline, or "project itinerary", you first should identify how the discrete tasks are related to one another, either sequentially, causally, or conceptually. Does the completion of one task require that another be undertaken first? Are there sets of tasks that can be carried out independently from others? Understanding these relationships will make it easier for you to define one or a number of workflows going forward.

As mentioned earlier, digital projects (like all scholarly projects) are iterative and subject to change and revision. Therefore, it is likely that your initial set of tasks, and the order in which you hope to complete them, will undergo expansion, contraction, and revision. As in sections I and II above, it is important that you record and date any such changes in direction, focus, or content when they occur, by using the "comments" boxes below each task field. Doing so will help you to keep track of your project's development, and eventually to narrate your project's inception and creation when you archive it with the DDP's [active](#) or [completed](#) project tools.

Add the tasks you will undertake by clicking the "add item" button for each entry. Use the "comments" section as tasks change or are completed.

Project Tasks

Task 1

a. Title of Task

Creación de perfiles profesionales

b. Task Description

Crear una serie de perfiles relacionados con los profesionales de la comunicación que sirvan de guía, con base en su formación profesional y expectativas laborales, para que los periodistas sepan qué curso o taller les puede servir.

c. Designated lead person for this task

Alma Cecilia Barajas

d. Email of designated lead

a01064713@itesm.mx

d. Task start date (anticipated)

8/15/2021

e. Task start date (actual)

8/30/2021

f. Task finish date (proposed)

9/15/2021

g. Task finish date actual

9/30/2021

h. Comments - updates and modifications**Task 2****a. Title of Task**

Contactar con instituciones periodísticas

b. Task Description

Comunicarse con los principales representantes de instituciones periodísticas para dar a conocer la plataforma digital y gestionar su inclusión en el catálogo de cursos a ofertar, considerando algún descuento especial para los visitantes de Periodistas en red.

c. Designated lead person for this task

Homero Hinojosa

d. Email of designated lead

homerohinojosa@tec.mx

d. Task start date (anticipated)

8/15/2021

e. Task start date (actual)

8/30/2021

f. Task finish date (proposed)

9/15/2021

g. Task finish date actual

9/30/2021

h. Comments - updates and modifications